

THE INFLUENCE OF MINERAL FERTILIZERS ON THE GROWTH
DYNAMICS OF ANNUAL BRANCHES OF MONKEY (RUBUS
FRUTICOSUS) PLANT

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Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада маймунжон (*rubus fruticosus*) навларига дала шароитида бўйига ўсиш динамикасига минерал ўғитларнинг таъсирига доир маълумотлар атрофлича ёритилган. Андижон вилояти Избоскан туманида жойлашган Академик Махмуд Мирзаев номидаги боғдорчилик, узумчилик ва виночилик илмий-тадқиқот институти Андижон илмий тажриба станцияси марказий дала майдонида олиб борилган тажрибаларга асосланиб маймунжон (*rubus fruticosus*) ўсимлигининг бўйига ўсиш динамикаси, минерал ўғитлар N₁₂₀ P₉₀ K₃₀+органик ўғит 20 тонна меъёрда қўлланилганда 2-option ўсимлик бўйи ўртача 130 см. ни ташкил қилди. Ушбу option Control optionга нисбатан ўсимликнинг ўсиши ва ривожланиши 28-38 фоизга юқори бўлгани кузатилди. Тажрибада optionлар орасидаги фарқ қўлланилган минерал ўғит таъсирида ўзгарганлиги аниқланди.

Аннотация. В статье подробно изложены сведения о влиянии минеральных удобрений на динамику роста сортов ежевики (*rubus fruticosus*) в полевых условиях. Динамика роста растений ежевики (*rubus fruticosus*), минеральные удобрения N₁₂₀ P₉₀ K₃₀+органическое удобрение из расчета 20 тонн, по данным опытов, проведенных на центральном поле НИИ садоводства, виноградарства и виноделия

имени академика Махмуда Мирзаева, расположенное в Избосканском районе Андижанской области, при использовании optiona 2 средняя высота растения составляет 130 см. Было замечено, что этот option показал рост и развитие растений на 28-38% выше по сравнению с контрольным optionом. В эксперименте установлено, что разница между optionами менялась под влиянием внесенного минерального удобрения.

Abstract. In this article, information on the effect of mineral fertilizers on the dynamics of height growth in the field conditions of rubus fruticosus varieties is detailed. Based on the experiments carried out in the central field of Andijan Scientific Experiment Station of Akademik Makhmud Mirzaev Research Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture and Winemaking named after Akademik Makhmud Mirzaev, Izboskan District, Andijan Region, the dynamics of growth of the mulberry (*Rubus fruticosus*) plant, mineral fertilizers N₁₂₀ P₉₀ K₃₀ + organic fertilizer at the rate of 20 tons option 2 plant when used average height is 130 cm. organized the It was observed that this variant showed 28-38% higher plant growth and development compared to the control variant. In the experiment, it was found that the difference between the options changed under the influence of the applied mineral fertilizer.

Калит сўзлар: Маймунжон, дала шароити, агротехника, бўйига ўсиш динамикаси, минерал ўғит, ўғит меъёри, Честер торнесс, Блек жем, Тройная корона.

Ключевые слова: Ежевика, полевые условия, агротехника, динамика роста по высоте, минеральное удобрение, норма удобрений, Честерская торнесс, Черный джем, Тройная корона.

Key words: Monkey, field conditions, agrotechnics, height growth dynamics, mineral fertilizer, fertilizer rate, Chester Torness, Black jam, Troynaya corona.

In the territory of our republic, many wild and cultivated species of berry crops grow and produce, which can be widely used in the fight against a number of diseases. In accordance with this, cultivation of medicinal plants that grow wild in the regions, development of agrotechnology for their cultivation on a scientific basis, and production of berry products on an industrial scale is one of the most urgent problems of today.

Monkeyberry (*Rubus fruticosus*) is a perennial shrub, a berry fruit, belonging to the ribis family. There are more than 1,350 wild species of monkeys, widely distributed in the temperate and subtropical regions of Eurasia. Cultivated varieties of monkey are common or red (*R. idaeus*), rough-

haired or American monkey (*R.strigosus*), western or monkey-like monkey (*R.occidentalis*) and other species. Cultivated in Central Asia, East Siberia, Far East, USA and European countries, the first hybrids were obtained in 1867 in Penn State, USA.

As a leader from the United States, by 1995, in the states of Oregon, California, Arkansas, for growing monkey fruits on an industrial scale, monkey cultivation became popular as a result of the production of 1,930,000 kilograms on an area of 2,500 hectares and export to European countries.

Due to the presence of carotene, ascorbic acid and tocopherol cobalamin, which are part of vitamin V, the fruit is widely used in the prevention of various infectious diseases, especially in the elimination of the complications of the SOVID-19 disease.

Monkey root is perennial, stem is biennial. The height of the bush is 3-10 m. Leaves appear simultaneously with the growth of the branch. The growth of leaves takes an average of 30-32 days. The leaves are three-lobed or five-seven-lobed, edged light green, hairy dark downy on both sides, complex, arranged in a row.

The flowers are white, some varieties are pink, bisexual, self-pollinating. The fruit is black, sometimes pink. In Uzbekistan, it blooms at the end of April and at the beginning of May. The flowers of the first order appear at the tip of the stem, the subsequent flower buds develop in the middle and lower parts. The fruit begins to ripen at the end of May-June, some varieties finish fruiting in the second half of August. The fruit has an aromatic taste, juicy, good, sweet, slightly sour, freshly picked fruits can be stored for 4-5 days in natural conditions.

Research methods. Research "Method and program for researching varieties of fruits, berries and nut plants" developed by the All-Russian Research Institute of Fruit Breeding (Oryol 1999); Biochemical and physiological researches were carried out in accordance with the "Method and program of testing varieties of fruit crops" (1973) of the Russian Research Institute of Horticulture named after I.V. Michurin.

Chester tornless, Black jam, Troynaya karon varieties of monkey were selected for research. Monkey seedlings 2.5x1 m. studied in planting schemes. The effect of different rates of NPK used in the experiment on the growth of one-year branches of the monkey cultivars was studied in 4 experiments as follows:

1-option $N_{120} P_{90} K_{30}$,

2- option $N_{120} P_{90} K_{30}$ +Organic fertilizer 20 tons,

3- option $N_{90} P_{67} K_{22}+$ Organic fertilizer 20 tons,

4- option Organic fertilizer 20 tons.

From this, 1-option, $N_{120}P_{90}K_{30}$, was taken as a control option.

№	Varieties name	Experiments	Counted plants, number of bushes	The number of branches counted	Growth dynamics of one-year branches cm	
					Sm	Relative to Control, %
1	Chester Tornless	1-option (Control)	5	15	211,8	100
		2- option	5	19	256,6	121
		3- option	5	17	238,2	113
		4- option	5	20	198,4	94
2	"Black Jam"	1- option (Control)	5	22	164,1	100
		2- option	5	18	205,5	126
		3- option	5	16	185,9	113
		4- option	5	15	142,7	86
3	"Troynaya Korona"	1- option (Control)	5	22	98,2	100
		2- option	5	24	135,8	137
		3- option	5	18	126,4	128
		4- option	5	16	84,1	85

According to the obtained data, the growth of the branches of the "Chester tornless" variety when $N_{120} P_{90} K_{30}+$ organic fertilizer 20 tons is used in the second option compared to the Control option is 44.8 cm. was higher. In the third option, $N_{90} P_{67} K_{22} +$ Organic fertilizer, 20 tons of norm was used, the growth of branches was 26.4 cm. was found to be long. 13.4 cm in the option of using 20 tons of organic fertilizer. It was observed that it grew low.

In the second option of Maimunjon variety "Black Jam" when the norms of $N_{120} P_{90} K_{30}+$ organic fertilizer 20 tons are applied, the growth of one-year branches is 41.4 cm compared to the Control option. was observed to grow high. In the third option, where the rate of $N_{90} P_{67} K_{22} +$ Organic fertilizer 20 tons was used, it was found that the growth of branches was 28.2 cm high. 21.4 cm compared to the

Control option in the option with tons of organic fertilizer₂₀. It was observed that it grew low.

37.6 cm in the option using the second $N_{120}P_{90}K_{30}$ +organic fertilizer 20 ton standards in Maimunjon variety "Troynaya Korona" compared to the Control option. showed the highest result, growing strongly to . In the third option, $N_{90}P_{67}K_{22}$ + Organic fertilizer 20 tons is used in the option, 28.2 cm. It was found that it was long and 14.1 cm in the option where tons of organic fertilizer₂₀ was used. It was observed that it grew low.

ХУЛОСА

1. When feeding monkey varieties with mineral fertilizers, the growth rate of one-year branches $N_{120}P_{90}K_{30}$ +organic fertilizer 20 tons and $N_{90}P_{67}K_{22}$ +organic fertilizer 20 tons is applied to the growth of "Chester Tornless" variety 44.8-26.3 cm compared to the Control option. It turned out that it grew rapidly. "Black Jam" variety 41.4-28.2 cm. It was found that it grew rapidly. 37.6-28.2 cm in the "Troynaya Korona" variety. established to

2. It was determined during the experiments that application of $N_{120}P_{90}K_{30}$ +organic fertilizer 20 tons and $N_{90}P_{67}K_{22}$ + Organic fertilizer 20 tons to growth dynamics of one-year branches of monkey varieties when fed with different proportions of mineral fertilizers gives good results.

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